

Effects of Safety Measures against Bomb Blasts in Kado Market of the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria

Odaudu, Ugbede Sunday¹ Abdullahi, Muhammad Usman²
Department of Architecture,
Kano University of Science and Technology, Wudil,
Nigeria.
arcodauduugbede@yahoo.com
+2348064069154

Abstract

Bomb blast in public places such as markets has been leading to the loss of lives and destruction of valuable properties in the northern part and Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. Hence, this problem brought a need for a research to be made in Kado market, since it is located in the FCT of Nigeria. The aim of the study is to determine the safety measures against bomb blasts in Kado market in Abuja, in order to provide policy recommendations to improve security in the FCT markets of Nigeria. The instruments that were used to collect the primary research data are the questionnaires administered to the 71 sales people and 71 buyers in the market via random sampling method in conjunction with focus group discussion that were made up of five sales people in 10 different groups. They are also the discussions that were made with the management staff of the market in conjunction with direct observation schedule. Secondary data were obtained from the reviews of materials that are relevant to this research. Tables and photographs were used as tools for the analysis of research data. Among the findings are: appropriate check against bomb blasts is poor in the market due to the lack of defined car parking spaces and this is leading to the indiscriminate parking of cars in any available space; the market has no patrol team to check for the activities of bombers that may arise within the market. Among the recommended guidelines are: markets should have defined car parking spaces to reduce indiscriminate parking of cars in any available space, in order to allow appropriate check against bomb blasts; market patrol team should be provided by the management authorities of markets, in order to check for activities of bombers that may arise within the markets.

Keywords: Bomb Blasts, Guidelines, Markets, Nigeria, Security.

1. INTRODUCTION

A bomb is basically a casing or shell that contains explosive materials (Scheve, 2017). The casing can be a steel-walled artillery shell, glass bottle or a sealed-shut length of lead pipe. Once the force of explosion is applied to the casing, it will fragment outward and each piece of the shell serving as a deadly projectile. A bomb can cause damages in different ways depending on the point at which there is impact of explosion. Frequent bomb blasts in Nigeria is traceable to Boko Haram Group (Walker, 2012). According to Anyadike (2013), Boko Haram Group is an Islamic sect that has formed a terrorist group because it wants to impose Islamic law on Nigeria; the group has posed security challenges on people and the entire government of Nigeria.

Bomb blast is one of the security challenges that has been significantly rated in Nigeria. The public places in the country have been experiencing bomb blasts from Boko Haram Group since August 2011 which have led to a severe threat on the socio-economic life in Nigeria (Walker, 2012). Markets are public places and authorised sites where people meet for trade or where goods and services are exchanged for money; they are where almost all the basic needs of people are sold in wholesales and retails (Chabbi-Chemrouk, 2007; Ngugi, 2015). Therefore, multitude of people go to market places for business transaction since they are public places where almost all the basic needs of people are sold. Hence, determining the passive and active safety measures against bomb blasts in Nigerian markets is absolutely very important for people since public places in Nigeria are prone to bomb blasts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the Centre for the Protection of National Infrastructure (2010), passive safety measures are ways in which buildings are designed against bomb blasts, while active safety measures are ways in which buildings are protected against bomb blasts by the use of security gargets and personnel. To design buildings such as markets for safety, needs a proactive approach which will anticipate and then protect the building users, structure, resources and continuity of operations that are free from multiple hazards (John, 2014). Bomb blast in public places such as markets is a problem in Nigeria which has led to the loss of many lives of people and destruction of different valuable properties. The majority

of bomb blasts have occurred in the northern part and Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria (Elijah *et al.*, 2015 and Walker, 2012). For example, 15 people were killed, while 20 people sustained varying degrees of wounds as a result of a bomb explosion in Kuje market of the FCT of Nigeria on 2nd October, 2015 (Cable, 2015 and Premium Times, 2015). Plate I shows the scene of a bomb blast in Kuje market. Also, on 18th November, 2015, there were twin bomb blasts that claimed the lives of 11 people in farm centre phone market in Kano, Kano State of Nigeria (BBC News, 2015a).

Plate I: Scene of a Bomb Blast in Kuje Market [Source: Cable, 2015
(<https://www.thecable.ng/breaking-abuja-hit-by-multiple-explosions>)].

In addition, more than 30 people were killed on 18th November, 2015b due to the bomb blasts in a busy vegetable market, Yola, Adamawa State of Nigeria (BBC News, 2015b). Moreover, at least 15 people were killed, while 18 people sustained injuries in a bomb blast in Konduga market, Borno State of Nigeria on 17th February, 2018 (Daily Post, 2018). Plate II shows the scene of a bomb blast in Konduga market. The need to conduct academic researches on bomb blasts in the northern part and FCT of Nigeria to curtail this problem is absolutely very crucial. Therefore, it became necessary to determine the safety measures against bomb blasts in Kado market in Abuja to improve security in the FCT markets of Nigeria, since FCT is the centre of Nigeria.

Plate II: Scene of a Bomb Blast in Konduga Market [Source: Daily Post, 2018 (<http://dailypost.ng/2018/02/17/15-feared-dead-boko-haram-bombs-borno-market/>)].

2.1 Aim and objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to determine the safety measures against bomb blasts in Kado market in Abuja, in order to provide policy recommendations to improve security in the FCT markets of Nigeria. Objectives of this study are: to evaluate the architectural design of Kado market against bomb blasts; to assess the availability and adequacy of security gargets against bomb blasts in Kado market; to analyse the adequacy and effectiveness of security personnel against bomb blasts in Kado market.

2.2 Scope of the study

The scope of this study is the entire Kado market with all its buildings and security infrastructures. Kado market is situated in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. The FCT of Nigeria is made up of six local councils which are the city of Abuja (Abuja Municipal Area Council) and the other five local councils; they are Abaji, Gwagwalada, Kuje, Bwari and Kwali (Satellite City Google Maps, 2016). Kado market is located along Jabi - Karimo road in Kado (off Public Works Quarters, and Jabi Reservoir) in Gwarimpa district; it is situated in Abuja Municipal Area Council of the FCT of Nigeria (Google Earth Map, 2016).

3. METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Descriptive survey method was adopted for this study; quantitative and qualitative data were generated. According to the Federal Capital Development Authority (2016), there are seven regional built-up markets under the control of FCT Markets Management Committee in the Federal Capital Development Authority of Nigeria. Purposive sampling method is known as judgmental, selective or subjective sampling due to the qualities the informants possess and usually, the samples being investigated are quite small with phenomenon of interest especially when compared with the probability sampling techniques (Etikan *et al.*, 2016; Lund Research Limited, 2012; Palinkas *et al.*, 2015). These seven regional built-up markets under the control of FCT Markets Management Committee are few in numbers. Thus, by using purposive sampling method, Kado market was selected for this study because according to the Abuja Markets Management Limited (2016), it is the most recent upgraded and established market in the FCT of Nigeria. Therefore, it became important that lessons should be learnt from this most recent upgraded market with regards to the safety measures against bomb blasts.

The instruments that were used to obtain the primary research data are questionnaires, discussions and direct observation schedule. According to the managing company of Kado market (Abuja Markets Management Limited, 2016), Kado market is comprised of 237 lock-up shops, 25 cold rooms/ware houses, three restaurants, 86 open stalls, one telecommunication centre and one clinic. Thus, by summing up the numbers of lock-up shops, cold rooms/ware houses, restaurants, open stalls, telecommunication centre and clinic in the market, it mathematically implies that there are 353 sales points in Kado market. 20% sample size of the target population of the study is a good recommended sample size (Prashant and Supriya, 2010; Steve, 2011; Suresh and Chandrashekara, 2012). Hence, 71 sales points in the market, and other infrastructures were studied via random sampling method. The 71 sales points selected for this study are slightly above 20% of the total number of sales points in the market and this in turn has made the sample size to be acceptable. In this case, questionnaires were administered to the 71 sales people in the selected sales points with the help of two research assistants. This means that in each selected sales point, a questionnaire was administered to one sales person. Hence, in the same method, questionnaires were also administered to the 71 buyers in the market.

According to Masadeh (2012) and Morgan *et al.* (2002), the outstanding benefits of using the method of focus group in a research is acquired in smaller groups of four or five participants. Thus, they were organised for the various categories of sales people in the market with the help of two research assistants that made it easier for the researchers to participate less in this aspect. In this research, focus group discussions that were made up of five sales people in 10 different groups were organised in the market. The reason for using up to 10 numbers of different focus groups in the market is to adequately and efficiently maximise the outstanding benefits of the research instrument or to get the maximum results from large numbers of the participants with respect to the size of the market in terms of the number of sales points in the market (353 sales points). In addition, discussions were made with the management staff of the market in conjunction with direct observation schedule to achieve the purpose of the study. Secondary data were obtained from the reviews of materials that are relevant to this research. Tables and photographs were used as tools for the analysis of research data.

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

In this section, data from the respondents with regards to the architectural design of the market against bomb blasts; the non-availability of security gargets against bomb blasts; the adequacy and effectiveness of the security personnel against bomb blasts in Kado market are discussed.

4.1 Architectural Design of the Market against Bomb Blasts

Most of the participants of this research responded that the architectural design of the market against bomb blasts is not adequate. Table 1 shows the responses from the questionnaires in respect of the percentages of adequacy and non-adequacy of the architectural design of the market against bomb blasts.

Table 1: Responses from the Questionnaires in Respect of the Percentages of Adequacy and Non-adequacy of the Architectural Design of Kado Market against Bomb Blasts.

S/N	Respondent	Number (Percentage) of Adequacy	Number (Percentage) of Non-adequacy
1	Sales People	26 (36.6%)	45 (63.4%)
2	Buyers	15 (21.1%)	56 (78.9%)

[Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2018].

The focus group discussion with sales people and the discussion with the management staff of the market revealed that the entire landmass of the market is fenced. It was observed that the fence walls are made up of sandcrete blocks with no burglary wire or any other security protective device on all parts of them to resist the bombers from jumping over them. The height of the fence walls in some areas is 1.6 metres with protective iron, while it is 2.0 metres in other areas without protective iron. This is not adequate enough to stop the bombers from invading the market. Plate III shows the part of fence walls with protective iron and the other part without any security protective device. It was observed that the market has up to three entrance gates. The discussion with the management staff showed that all of them are not bomb detecting type. It was observed that the market is not landscaped to check the movement of bombers; if the bombers can find their ways into the market, attacking people will be easy. Plate IV shows the part of the market without ground cover for landscape.

Plate III: Part of the Fence Walls with Protective Iron and the other Part without any Security Protective Device [Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2018].

Plate IV: Part of the Market without Ground Cover for Landscape [Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2018].

It was observed that there are no defined car parking spaces in the market and as a result of this, people park cars indiscriminately in any available space. In this case, appropriate security check against bomb blasts is very poor because the bombers can use this chance to

bomb the market. It was also observed that the buildings in the market are made up of sandcrete block walls; when there are bomb blasts on this type of walls, they can collapse easily. In addition, it was observed that some buildings in the market were designed such that their walls are joint together with inadequate space of about 2.5 metres between them, and thereby making their roofs to appear like folded type of roof. In this case, when one building is affected by bomb blast, the probability of the second building to be damaged is high. Plate V shows the joint buildings in the market.

Plate V: Joint buildings in the Market [Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2018].

4.2 Non-availability of Security Gargets against Bomb Blasts in the Market

The focus group discussion with sales people and the discussion with the management staff of the market revealed that the security gargets such as Closed-circuit Television (CCTV) Cameras and detectors against bomb blasts are not available in the market.

4.3 Adequacy and Effectiveness of Security Personnel against Bomb Blasts in the Market

Most of the participants of this research responded that the security personnel against bomb blasts in the market are not adequate. Table 2 shows the responses from the questionnaires in respect of the percentages of adequacy and non-adequacy of security personnel against bomb blasts in the market.

Table 2: Responses from the Questionnaires in Respect of the Percentages of Adequacy and Non-adequacy of Security Personnel against Bomb Blasts in Kado Market.

S/N	Respondent	Number (Percentage) of Adequacy	Number (Percentage) of Non-adequacy
1	Sales People	5 (7%)	66 (93%)
2	Buyers	2 (2.8%)	69 (97.2%)

[Source: Researchers' Field Work, 2018].

The focus group discussion with the sales people showed that the incoming vehicles to the market are not checked against bomb blasts. Also, the discussion with the management staff of the market revealed that the market has no patrol team. In this case, there are no check for activities of bombers that may arise within the market.

5. NORMALITY TEST

Percentages were used to present all the data collected via the questionnaires administered to the sales people and buyers. This means that the parameter that was used for the analysis of data collected via the questionnaires administered to the sales people and buyers is percentage. Hence, by adopting the numerical and visual methods of normality test for the parametric analysis, the percentage parameters were normally and appropriately distributed throughout the whole analyses, and these have made the results of data analyses to be acceptable because they are in line with the rules of normality test (Fitrianto and Chin,

2016; Jason, 2018; OpenAnesthesia, 2018; Statistics and Data Sciences, 2015; UC Business Analytics, 2018). Similarly, by adopting the visual method of normality test for the content analyses, the results of content analyses were accepted because of the normal and appropriate comparisons of the research data within the themes and sub-themes. In the same dimension, these are in line with the rules of normality test (Bengtsson, 2016; Hawkins, 2013; Library Guides, 2018; Spyros, 2015).

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Having considered the causes and negative effects of bomb blasts in the northern part and Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria. To this end, Kado market of the FCT of Nigeria was studied since FCT is the centre of Nigeria, and the aim was to assess the safety measures against bomb blasts in the market, in order to provide policy recommendations to improve security in the FCT markets of Nigeria.

The research findings showed that: the architectural design of the market against bomb blasts is not adequate; the fence walls are made up of sandcrete blocks with no burglary wire or any other security protective device on all parts of them to resist the bombers from jumping over them; the height of the fence walls in some areas is 1.6 metres with protective iron, while it is 2.0 metres in other areas without protective iron, and this is not adequate enough to stop the bombers from invading the market; the entrance gates to the market are not bomb detecting type; the market is not landscaped to check the movement of bombers; appropriate check against bomb blasts is very poor in the market due to the lack of defined car parking spaces and this is leading to the indiscriminate parking of cars in any available space; buildings in the market are made up of sandcrete block walls, and when there are bomb blasts on this type of walls, they can collapse easily; some buildings in the market were designed with inadequate space of about 2.5 metres between them, and in this case, when one building is affected by bomb blast, the probability of the second building to be damaged is high.

Other research findings are: the security gargets against bomb blasts such as CCTV cameras and bomb detectors are not available in the market; the security personnel against bomb blasts in the market are not adequate; the incoming vehicles to the market are not checked against bomb blasts; the market has no patrol team to check for the activities of bombers that may arise within the market. Therefore, the following policy recommendations are provided to improve security against bomb blasts in the FCT markets of Nigeria:

- i. All the market fences must have burglary wire or any other protective device on them to resist the bombers from jumping over them.
- ii. Market fences should not be less than 2.4 metres height to stop the bombers from invading markets.
- iii. The entrance gates to the markets must be bomb detecting type.
- iv. Markets should be landscaped to check the movement of bombers.
- v. Markets should have defined car parking spaces to reduce indiscriminate parking of cars in any available space, in order to allow appropriate check against bomb blasts.
- vi. Market fences and other buildings in markets should be made up of concrete or stone walls or any other strong walling material to be able to resist bomb blasts.
- vii. The spaces between market buildings should not be less than eight metres during the design and construction stages to reduce the damages of buildings, in case of bomb blasts.
- viii. Markets must have security gargets such as CCTV cameras and detectors against bomb blasts.
- ix. Adequate security personnel against bomb blasts in markets should be provided by the management authorities of markets.
- x. The incoming vehicles to the markets must be checked against bomb blasts.
- xi. Market patrol team should be provided by the management authorities of markets, in order to check for activities of bombers that may arise within the markets.

This research did not consider the fear of bomb blasts and the psychological effects of the fear on the users of the market that was studied; this is a gap in knowledge. Therefore, in subsequent research of this kind, this gap should be filled.

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Author(s)

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Odaudu, Ugbede Sunday

He is a Graduate of Architecture with both Bachelor and Master of Technology Degrees from Federal University of Technology, Minna, Nigeria. He is currently rounding up his Doctorate Degree Programme in the Department of Architecture of the same university. He is currently a Member of different Professional Organisations; among others are: an Associate Member of Nigerian Institute of Architects (NIA), and a member of Association of Architectural Educators (AARCHES) in Nigeria, National Association for Research Development (NARD) in Nigeria, and Nationwide Association for the Advancement of Knowledge (NAFAK) in Nigeria. He started lecturing job career in the Department of Architectural Technology, Nigerian Army Institute of Technology and Environmental Studies, Markudi in January, 2015 and later joined Kano University of Science and Technology (KUST), Wudil, Nigeria in December, 2015 till date as the same lecturer in the Department of Architecture. Among other current responsibilities in KUST are: Member of Academic Board at both Departmental and Faculty Levels, Member of Seminar Committee at Faculty Level, Member of the Committee in Charge of Curriculum and Handbook Course Synopsis of the Department of Architecture, Assistant Postgraduate Coordinator of the Department of Architecture, and Assistant Postgraduate Examination Officer of the Department of Architecture.

2

Abdullahi, Muhammad Usman

He is a graduate of Architecture with Bachelor of Science Degree in 2006 from Kano University of Science and Technology (KUST), Wudil, Nigeria. He also has Master Degree in Architecture in 2016 from SRM University, Chennai, India. He has worked with Xmatrix 369 from 2008 to 2010, and Bashtima International from 2010 to 2011 as Chief Architect. He has been a lecturer in the Department of Architecture, KUST since 2012 till date.